

**Review of: O'Meara, Dominic, *Cosmology and Politics in Plato's Later Works*,
Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2017**

October 8, 2020

[*Final/published version in Review of Metaphysics 74 (2), Dec. 2020*]

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It goes without saying that Plato's late dialogues (e.g. *Laws*, *Sophist*, *Philebus*, etc.) have experienced a renaissance in scholarship in recent years. Tying together previous and recent contributions on the subject, Dominic O'Meara's book provides a new, comprehensive survey of Plato's political philosophy set against the background of Plato's metaphysics and cosmology in the late dialogues. Not only does the book build on recent scholarship, but it also does something rather new: O'Meara focuses on cultural, religious, and technical contexts in the dialogues which are essential to illustrate the analogical connections Plato draws between the two domains of metaphysical, or cosmological, structure—the world of nature that is—and political structure—the world of humans that should attempt to be. These concrete contexts in turn reveal a central thesis throughout O'Meara's book: the paradigms, or principles, that Plato discusses should be understood as generic sketches which imply a multiplicity of possible instantiations, both in the cosmos and in good cities.

O'Meara lays out his reading in two sections: the cosmological account in the *Timaeus* (Chapters 1–4), and the city of the *Statesman* and the *Laws* (Chapters 5–7). Chapter 1 discusses the symposium-style feast in which the *Timaeus* is situated, where the re-telling of ancient Athens' victory over Atlantis throws into relief the presence of a virtuous Athens that no longer exists during the events of the *Timaeus*' own time: the cosmological story that Timaeus himself retells, as O'Meara concludes, is intended to lead to the story of the excellent state and its exploits. This leads to Chapter 2 on the world-maker's nature in Timaeus' speech, which is in honor to an unnamed god—as O'Meara

¹ The author would like to thank the European Research Council for their support in the production of this review, within the framework of the project, NeoplAT (ERC_CoG_771640).

concludes, to Zeus, however a very different “Zeus” than the familiar one of Greek mythology. This new, “reformed” conception should be reflected in the legislative, political sense of the very word for the world creator, *dêmiourgos*, related to the term, *dêmios*, i.e. “public”. O’Meara concludes that Timaeus’ speech is supposed to highlight the *craft*, or skill, of the *dêmiourgos*, rather than the identity of the creator itself, as most significant for the order of the world—and therein the conditions for the good city’s emergence.

Chapter 3 considers what this “craft” is, i.e. the model (*paradeigma*) according to which the world is ordered by the *dêmiourgos*: perhaps one of the book’s most interesting analyses, O’Meara discusses blueprint plans (*paradeigmata*) used in Ancient Greek architecture, where the first, main plan provided only a generalized sketch of the building before the builders began their construction, where, then, a *second* set of plans (*paradeigmata*) would be drafted for specific parts not yet considered in the first plans. O’Meara argues for a parallel in the world-building of Timaeus’ story: the creator’s *paradeigma*, the Living Animal-itself, is only a sketch from which the creator begins building the cosmos, while the “second”, detailed set of plans can be seen, e.g. in the creator’s mandate for the lower gods’ subsequent production process. This leads to Chapter 4’s corollary on the relation of beauty and goodness in the cosmos, where—though the two terms are closely interrelated—“beauty” in the world is the realization of the good manifested in the *paradeigma* sketched for the world.

This theme is brought out in Chapter 5’s discussion of “weaving”—as one sees in the new robe made for Athena in the Panathenaic festival—and its relation to the skill of statesmanship, as a directive science, albeit in a general, non-specific sense—much like the cosmos’ non-detailed *paradeigma*. Chapter 6 considers the necessity for the legislators of the *Laws*’ city to examine legislation continuously—as exercising this “weaving”—in relation to the goal of abiding by the persisting *paradeigma* of the city. And finally Chapter 7 considers the city’s respective *paradeigma* from the *Laws*, where O’Meara spells out the specific parallelism between the cosmos’ order and that of the city (pp. 122–125): e.g. the proportionality between the soul and four elements constituting bodies, as in *Timaeus*, can also be seen in the proportion which unifies and differentiates the city’s inhabitants. In this paralleling, O’Meara especially focuses on the role of religion in the city as the central, unifying

force which habituates the order paralleled in the cosmos: the three, main gods behind the city and its religion, whoever they may be, are ultimately “the rationality which makes the universe good and beautiful, the knowledge of this rationality which legislators should have” (p. 132).

O’Meara’s book, though relatively short (~140 pp.), is a deeply interesting, penetrating, and innovative read which helps shed light on the broader vision of Plato’s late period. It will certainly be a benchmark from which—one may hope—more work may be done on the intersection between politics and metaphysics, both in Plato’s late dialogues and more generally in the Old Academy.